

Speech emotion recognition using 2D-convolutional neural network

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ABSTRACT

This research proposes a speech emotion recognition model to predict human emotions using the convolutional neural network (CNN) by learning segmented audio of specific emotions. Speech emotion recognition utilizes the extracted features of audio waves to learn speech emotion characteristics; one of them is mel frequency cepstral coefficient (MFCC). Dataset takes a vital role to obtain valuable results in model learning. Hence this research provides the leverage of dataset combination implementation. The model learns a combined dataset with audio segmentation and zero padding using 2D-CNN. Audio segmentation and zero padding equalize the extracted audio features to learn the characteristics. The model results in 83.69% accuracy to predict seven emotions: neutral, happy, sad, angry, fear, disgust, and surprise from the combined dataset with the segmentation of the audio files.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) studies show enormous beneficial growth in most aspects of the product industry. One of the studies in AI that gather the researcher's attention is affective computing with all its humanitarian approaches. Affective computing recognizes, processes, and produces human feelings using a computational approach [1]. It reaches many fields in the industry, such as medic, psychotherapy, marketing, and advertising [2]. The implementation of emotion detection expands facial expression recognition, language recognition, empathy giving, and other functionalities closer to how humans function. In addition, emotion recognition widens the technology growth of affective computing itself. Emotion recognition is human feelings recognition of many data sources, from texts, facial expressions, voices, gestures, and behaviors [3]–[5].

Researchers face two main focuses to solve in speech emotion recognition. They are the extracted feature selection and model selection. Speech emotion recognition is an emotion recognition of human speech using computation models in affective computing and develops forensic, security, and biometric fields [6]. Besides its lexical contents, human speech expresses other characteristics: information of age, gender, language, and emotion [6], [7]. The audio contains many features to extract into computational form by transforming audio to a graph of arrays. The extraction of speech waveform is categorized into four: prosodic, spectral, audio quality, and Teager energy operator features [8]. Extracted audio features are mel frequency cepstral coefficient (MFCC), spectrogram, zero crossing rate (ZCR), Teager energy operator (TEO), harmonic to noise rate (HNR) [9]–[12]. In emotion recognition, MFCC is a cepstral domain feature used the most for research [12].

For decades, speech emotion recognition has been done and delivered different results and developments. Extracted audio feature selection takes effect on emotion prediction results. Based on prior research, researchers often use MFCC, and the feature results in better performance [10], [13]–[15]. To maximize the usage of those features, segmentation on speech data may enhance the accuracy of emotion prediction, like what Yeh *et al.* [16]. They produced a series of segments by parting a segment of existing speech from a long audio track. A frame-based segmentation applied well to a track of singular emotion speech, but voiced segmentation is better to apply in a long speech.

Learning the emotions can be done by using models of deep learning. The growth of emotion recognition systems is also affected by learning models, like deep learning, which can recognize image structures of voices and facial expressions [1]. A deep learning advantage for emotion recognition is the automation of feature selection that contains important emotion attributes of the data source, especially audio [17].

Researchers use the classification models to classify emotions from extracted audio features. Some of them are convolutional neural network (CNN), recurrent neural network (RNN), and support vector machine (SVM) [10], [14], [17] among those classification models, CNN is confident in processing pictures and applying them to speech emotion recognition since the extracted audio features form can be a picture. Prior research of speech emotion recognition shows that CNN produces higher accuracy than RNN and SVM models [14], [18]. This condition allows us to choose CNN as the platform for the speech emotion recognition model. CNN architecture consists of an input layer, convolutional layer, pooling layer, fully-connected layer, and output layer sequentially [19]. The essential operation of CNN is in the convolution and pooling process; the convolution process uses filters to extract feature maps of datasets where beneficial information is maintained, pooling or subsampling process reduces feature maps dimension [20] and could benefit in reverberant conditions [21]. CNN shows its confidence in learning emotions for speech emotion recognition with high accuracy [13]–[15], [22].

Speech emotion recognition research uses many audio data from datasets that vary in languages, duration, and emotions. Most speech emotion recognition research uses datasets equipped with emotion labels. Some of the datasets used by researchers are Ryerson audio-visual database of emotional speech and song (RAVDESS), surrey audio-visual expressed emotion (SAVEE), The interactive emotional dyadic motion capture (IEMOCAP), Toronto emotional speech set (TESS), CASIA, dan EMO [9], [11], [14], [15], [22], [23]. The work to combine datasets is expanded by de Pinto *et al.* [15] to gain a model with better performance. They combined the RAVDESS speech and TESS datasets to minimize their prior work's overfitting condition using one-dimensional convolutional network; hence, it reached a better model than the particular dataset from their prior work. Overfitting is the network's inability to learn data effectively for various reasons, such as problems in learning noise in the data train, imbalanced variance and bias, and ineffective architecture [24]. The combination of datasets may deliver more significant data quantities to enhance the model performance on learning more training sets.

Therefore, compared to prior works, we propose a different approach: implementing a two-dimensional convolutional neural network (2D-CNN) that utilizes MFCC features and audio segmentation with a larger dataset. We combine RAVDESS, SAVEE, and TESS datasets. The three datasets have similar pitch-based emotions and similar audio lengths with seven same emotions: neutral, sad, happy, angry, disgust, fear, and surprise. We deliver a 2D-CNN by adding MFCC as an additional dimension in our classification model.

2. METHOD

2.1. Dataset

First of all, we find all available labelled speech audio datasets on the internet. The chosen datasets are the ones that fulfil the needs of experiments such as having similar emotions, similar track duration, and the works of literature that used the datasets. In this research, we picked several high-quality datasets with useful similarities for learning since it causes the possibility of accuracy reduction of deep learning algorithms to be minimized [25].

The collected datasets are RAVDESS, SAVEE, and TESS, which have exactly one emotion in each audio track and range from one to five seconds of duration in each track. RAVDESS is a database of audio speech and song in English with eight validated emotions [26]. RAVDESS has 24 actors who expressed neutral, calm, happy, sad, angry, fear, surprise, and disgust in a total of 1,440 speech data. SAVEE is a recorded visual and audio dataset from four researchers at the University of Surrey [2]. SAVEE has seven emotions: anger, disgust, fear, happiness, sadness, and surprise, expressed in English with 480 tracks. TESS (Toronto emotional speech set) is a set of audio from two actresses who expressed seven emotions: anger, disgust, fear, happiness, sad, neutral, and pleasant surprise [27]. The TESS dataset consists of 2,800 audio files in English.

2.2. Preprocessing

The preprocessing data step consists of segmentation, audio feature extraction, and zero padding of MFCC. We use Python in the Jupyter Notebook equipped with Librosa, Numpy, operating systems (OS), and JSON libraries to do this preprocessing step. Two types of segmentation models were carried out in the experiment, namely linear segmentation and overlap segmentation. Linear segmentation cuts voice recordings sequentially, without any segments having data in common. Overlap segmentation cuts voice recordings by making data slices that intersect in each segment. The sample MFCC data on RAVDESS Figure 1(a) after segmentation is Figure 1(b) for linear segmentation and Figure 1(c) for overlap segmentation. Next, to avoid leaving important parts behind segmentation and help each segment to have the same length, we use zero padding on imperfect segments. Zero padding helps the imperfect segments to reach the target length by padding the transposed MFCC array of the segment with zeros. The MFCC array is transposed first to be processed in classification later. Figure 1(d) shows the applied zero padding on an imperfect segment.

Figure 1. Transformation of MFCC of audio sample in RAVDESS, from (a) an original MFCC data before preprocessing steps, then after preprocessing steps; (b) linear segmentation of one-second duration; (c) overlap segmentation of two-second duration; and (d) zero padding on a segment.

2.3. Emotion classification experiments

The processing data step consists of the emotion classification by experimenting on the model architecture and datasets. In this step, we use Python in the Jupyter Notebook equipped with TensorFlow, Sklearn, Numpy, JSON, dan Matplotlib libraries. The JSON file of the dataset will be loaded then grouped into sets such as train set, test set, and validation set. The MFCC array is then formed into a three-dimensional array by adding a new axis as depth. The three-dimensional shape represents the length of MFCC, the number of MFCC, and the visual color of the picture. For instance, one represents grayscale, and three represents red, green, blue (RGB) color.

The CNN architecture is built using the Keras library from TensorFlow. It consists of essential CNN layers: convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers, which are stacked sequentially in a model. We use a block of convolutional layers consisting of a 2D convolutional layer, a 2D max-pooling layer, and a batch normalization layer. The convolutional layer is activated using the ReLu function. The next layer is a flattening layer for deducting the shape into one vector data; hence the data can be classified. After

the flattening layer, a fully connected layer is implemented to classify. The output layer is activated using the SoftMax function. The learning process uses the Adam optimizer from Keras with the loss calculated by sparse categorical cross-entropy.

We do some experiments for model enhancement to avoid overfitting, including model performance improvements. There are three aspects in our experiments: CNN network, learning process, and dataset. In the experiments of CNN network, we focus on layers, filters, and also regularization. In the aspect of the learning process, the independent parameters used are the dataset allocation ratio, batch size, and epochs. Furthermore, as the other aspects, we also have some experiments in the dataset aspect, which are segmentation and duration. In the end, all experiments from these three aspects will produce the best-experimental model.

2.4. Evaluation

The evaluation step will rate the performance of the model. The best-experimented model from processing data steps is used to predict emotions from a prepared dataset sample. The model will show the prediction of some samples' emotions. Then, we evaluate the model's performance by measuring its precision, recall, and F1-score. Next, the model is compared with other models to see the quality of its performance.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Preprocessing data

Preprocessing step includes segmentation, feature extraction, and zero padding. Each track has a different duration length from one to another. As we use a frame-based segmentation, we first decide the length of the segment by analyzing the length of the tracks. We consider the possible length of the segment to be between one to three seconds. Then, a duration length experiment will evaluate the best length for the segment.

We use the two types of frame-based segmentation model, namely linear segmentation and overlap segmentation. After the segmentation, the MFCC feature of each segment is extracted. We use 13 MFCCs; therefore, the shape of extracted MFCC is (13, n). For classification, we transpose the array to the shape of (n, 13). Because the segmentation may have leftover segments with less than the desired length, zero padding is applied to help the segments reach the desired length. We pad the MFCC array using zeros to the desired shape. In audio data, this means adding silent audio to the segment. For example, for a three-second segment with a shape of (130, 13), on a (52, 13) segment, we add (78, 13) zeros to it, so it reaches the desired shape (130, 13). After the entire segments are ready, we save them into JSON list data. Table 1 presents the number of segments in each dataset.

Table 1. Preprocessing data results

Duration	Dataset	Emotions							Total
		N	H	Sad	A	F	D	Sur	
2s	RAVDESS	193	401	408	450	397	461	389	2699
	SAVEE	270	142	166	141	140	148	141	1148
	TESS	663	567	798	564	107	800	583	4082
	Total	1126	1110	1372	1155	744	1409	1113	7929
3s	RAVDESS	192	384	384	384	384	384	383	2495
	SAVEE	215	105	119	107	107	113	106	872
	TESS	400	400	400	400	400	400	400	2800
	Total	807	889	903	891	891	897	889	6167

3.2. Processing data

Processing data is the process of training a model to classify emotions. The first thing to do in processing data is load data. We pick the prepared dataset in loading data and then convert the MFCC arrays into a four-dimensional array to value its depth of color dimension. The shape of MFCC arrays is now (m, n, 13, 1) with m as the number of segments and n as the MFCC length. MFCC arrays are the classification data. Emotion labels are the classification targets. The data are then grouped into three categories: train set, test set, and validation set with a ratio of 5:3:2 to 8:1:1.

The proposed architecture of CNN Network consists of 2D convolutional blocks, a flattening layer, and a fully connected layer. The model is affected by the parameters we choose in model optimization. The model optimization applied in this research is shown in Table 2.

Each experiment is held under the same circumstances to check different effects from assigned parameters. The result shows unexpected overfitting conditions in several experiments. Through the experiments, we could define better parameters to minimize overfitting conditions. For example, in dropout

experiments, implementing dropout reduces the overfitting because dropout updates the outgoing edges of neurons to zero. Implementing regularizers also minimize overfitting since they ease model learning complexity. In our case, the primary reason overfitting happens is the small quantity dataset. The epochs experiment shows that a small quantity dataset would result in overfitting as adding the number of epochs.

Table 2. Experimental table

Aspect	Experiments	Parameters	Results (Avg of Acc)
CNN Network	Layers experiments	Two convolutional layer blocks	66.05%
		Three convolutional layer blocks	63.67%
	Filter shape experiments	3×3 and 3×3	62.34%
		3×3 and 2×2	67.96%
		2×2 and 3×3	63.40%
		2×2 and 2×2	66.58%
	Filter amount experiments	32 and 32	63.15%
		32 and 64	67.05%
		64 and 32	68.01%
		64 and 64	69.99%
	Dropout layer experiments	No dropout	71.88% (Overfitting)
		One dropout 0.5	73.99% (Overfitting)
Two dropouts 0.5		66.69%	
Regularization experiments	No regularizer	67.45% (Overfitting)	
	With regularizer l2	66.94%	
Learning Process	Dataset ratio allocation experiments	5:3:2	69.26%
		7:2:1	67.67%
		8:1:1	70.61%
	Batch size experiments	44	71.19%
		72	68.29%
		100	68.83%
Epochs experiments	30	72.45%	
	70	73.91% (Overfitting)	
	100	74.12% (Overfitting)	
Dataset	Duration experiments	2 secs	66.93%
		3 secs	67.18%
	Segmentation experiments	Linear segmentation	63.71%
		Overlap segmentation	66.59%

The best model is formed by all those experimented parameters, which results in the highest accuracy. As shown in Table 2, the best model has two convolutional layer blocks, two dropout layers, a flattening layer, and a fully connected layer. In addition, it has filters with 3×3 and 2×2 shapes, the number of filters of 64 and 64, and regularizer L2 for CNN architecture. The dataset used to learn best combines three datasets (RAVDDESS, SAVEE, and TESS) with overlap segmentation of three-second segments. For learning the model, we use 44 batch sizes, 30 epochs, and a dataset ratio of 8:1:1. Here is the model summary presented in Figure 2 and the model performance in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Model summary

3.3. Evaluation

In the evaluation step, firstly, we calculate the precision score, recall score, and F1-score of the model to know its performance. The dataset used is a combination of three datasets with overlap segmentation of three seconds duration. The model accuracy from the evaluation of combined datasets is

83.69%. It reaches higher accuracy because the prediction includes the same data for training. Next, we make predictions of 500 samples from the dataset containing 61 neutral, 72 happy, 74 sad, 72 angry, 74 fear, 75 disgust, and 72 surprised. From the confusion matrix, we can see the correct and false predictions. The precision, recall, and F1-score are then calculated from the correct and false predictions. We can see the scores of each emotion in Table 3. Overall, the model has an average precision score of 73.65%, a recall of 73.77%, and an F1-score of 73.63% on 500 data samples.

Figure 3. Model performance

Table 3. Precision, recall, and F1-score from the model

Emotions	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Data Count
Neutral	0.7246	0.8197	0.7692	61
Happy	0.6800	0.7083	0.6939	72
Sad	0.6944	0.6757	0.6849	74
Angry	0.8088	0.7639	0.7857	72
Fear	0.7794	0.7162	0.7465	74
Disgust	0.7922	0.8133	0.8026	75
Surprise	0.6761	0.6667	0.6713	72
Accuracy			0.7360	500
Average	0.7365	0.7377	0.7363	500

After that, we evaluate the performance of the dataset combination by comparing it to each dataset. The model learns each dataset using the same test set. The comparison results in the accuracy of 40.19%, 17.99%, 53.65%, and 69.21% for the dataset RAVDESS, SAVEE, TESS, and the combination of three of them, respectively. The combination result shows higher accuracy than any individual dataset, meaning that a dataset combination could raise the model accuracy in predicting emotions.

We also compare our model to other models to see which one performs better. We experimented with the chosen combined dataset. The models to compare are CNN 1-D and RNN long short-term memory (RNN-LSTM). The CNN 1-D model uses the architecture of Pinto *et al.* [15]. The architecture of RNN-LSTM model is two LSTM layers, each followed by a dropout layer and one dense layer. The models are experimented with using similar learning process configurations on the same test set. The comparison results in 69.21%, 51.05%, and 58.02% accuracy for CNN 2-D, CNN 1-D, and RNN-LSTM, respectively. From the comparison, we can see that our proposed model, the CNN 2-D, works better than the other two.

4. CONCLUSION

This research implements a 2D-CNN model to predict emotions from speech using RAVDESS, SAVEE, and TESS datasets. The extracted audio feature is mel frequency cepstral coefficient (MFCC). A frame-based segmentation is done to the audio files to get the same audio length. Each segment with less length will be padded with zeros on its MFCC array.

The optimum dataset is chosen by segmentation and combination experiments. The CNN architecture is built using experiments for model optimization, such as layers, filters, and regularizers. In addition, experiments of batch size, epochs, and dataset ratio composition optimize the learning process. The proposed model reaches 83.69% accuracy on three datasets using overlap segmentation for three-second segments. In addition, the model can classify seven emotions: neutral, happy, sad, angry, fear, disgust, and surprise. The developments for speech emotion recognition may vary. However, this research recommends the robustness of deep learning models using data augmentation techniques, building a more effective classification model, and using more precise audio features to recognize the emotion better.

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